

A Robust Design Methodology Process

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Abstract

Robust Design Methodology (RDM) has been established as an approach to design products that are reliable and have stable performance despite exposure to variation in uncontrollable factors. Research on RDM has traditionally focused on the application of various tools to support RDM. Less has been written on how RDM practices can be applied throughout a product development (PD) process. This paper presents a study of a medium-sized manufacturing company working with a Product Robustness Process (PRP). PRP is a sub-process in their PD, and focuses mainly on practices supporting RDM and the outcome in terms of increased robustness. An example of a practice is to systematically identify factors that will vary under operating conditions and affect product performance and reliability. By knowledge of such factors it is possible to take robustness into account in early PD phases. In some phases of the PRP, indications of suitable tools are given, however not as a compulsory prescription. The PRP shows how practices of RDM can be made a part of an established PD process. It also aims to focus on practices, rather than tools or techniques, to maximise RDM application. Case studies on RDM are often focusing on tools such as Design of Experiments; albeit important it is of value to consider daily RDM practices without necessarily involving a prescribed tool. This paper aims at contributing to the latter by means of a case study at a company working with a PRP for about two years. The purpose of the paper is to describe and evaluate a process for RDM practices throughout PD. The most important outcome of the PRP is that the development teams have relised a systematic way to address quality and reliability on the agenda throughout PD.

1. Introduction

Robust Design Methodology (RDM) aims at creating products with stable performance despite exposure to variation in uncontrollable factors, so-called noise factors, e.g. variations in operational temperature or customer usage (Arvidsson and Gremyr, 2008). A common visualization of a robust design is the so called p-diagram (Phadke, 1989). This diagram displays the product as affected by control as well as noise factors, where the settings of the control factors are used to create a design that is insensitive to the influence of the noise factors. The outcome is a reliable and stable performance, which do not only have effects on customer satisfaction but also results in less scrap, waste and re-work. Thus, RDM is an engineering methodology that could enhance environmental or economic sustainability (Gremyr et al., 2014).

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Reduction of variation is an important area in quality management ((Shoemaker et al., 1991), (Thornton et al., 2000), (Taguchi et al., 2005)). As stated by Box and Bisgaard (1988) “The enemy of mass production is variability. Success in reducing it will invariably simplify processes, reduce scrap, and lower costs”. A link to sustainability is pointed out when defining quality loss as “the amount of functional variation of products plus all possible negative effects, such as environmental damages and operational costs” (Taguchi, 1993).

As an engineering methodology it is argued here that RDM is not merely a set of tools or techniques, but also consists of a number of principles and practices. Principles are the basic assumptions that are implemented through practices, i.e. activities done in support of the basic assumptions (Dean and Bowen, 1994). Practices are then supported by various techniques. In line with this way of operationalizing concepts, RDM has been defined as “systematic efforts to achieve insensitivity to noise factors. These efforts are founded on an awareness of variation and can be applied in all stages of product development.” (Arvidsson and Gremyr, 2008).

Textbooks, e.g.(O’Connor, 2002), present various statistically based tools for the development of robust and reliable products. Discussion of statistical tools supportive of RDM has taken place in a number of papers over the years e.g. (León et al., 1987), (Box, 1988), (Shainin and Shainin, 1988), (Welch et al., 1990), and (Robinson et al., 2004). The most commonly discussed tool is Design of Experiments, see e.g. (Shoemaker and Kackar, 1988), (Shoemaker et al., 1991), (Box and Jones, 1992) and (Ellekjær and Bisgaard, 1998). As much focus has been on the application of statistical tools supporting RDM, the early and more conceptual stages of product development have received less attention. However, (Ford, 1996) and (Anderson, 1997) points at the need of applying RDM efforts in the conceptual design. Further, it has been argued that there is a need to identify RDM practices suitable for all parts of a product development process (Hasenkamp et al., 2009).

The basis for this paper is a case study at a Swedish medium-sized manufacturing company, hereafter referred to as MC, aiming to develop a Product Robustness Process (PRP) as a sub-process in their product development. MC is developing, producing and selling their own patented high-tech product used by individual end users. The company is about 15 years old and has about 250 employees. The purpose of this paper is to describe and evaluate a process for RDM practices throughout PD. The continuation of this paper is structured as follows: a method chapter accounting for the study performed, followed by a description of the needs of the company related to robustness, and a description of the PRP. The final parts of the paper contain discussion and conclusions.

2. Method

The study has been performed by three researchers; one employed by MC (later referred to as internal researcher) and two university-employed external researchers. The study has taken place for a year, following MC’s work on developing their PRP. For the external researchers the study has involved about ten meetings of 2-3 hours each discussing alternative designs of the PRP, as well as numerous e-mails and telephone calls reflecting on drafts of the PRP. The internal researcher is responsible for the PRP at MC. Hence, this research has been carried out as an action research, in other words research with rather than on local players with an explicit intention to improve the system studied (Coghlan and Brannik, 2008).

The empirical data consisted of meeting notes, drafts of the PRP, material related to MC’s product development process, discussions with staff involved in the PRP and observations by the internal researcher. In order to strengthen the creative potential of the study and increase confidence in the findings, multiple investigators (internal and external researcher) worked

jointly on the analysis (Eisenhardt, 1989). Further, the internal and the external researchers wrote the paper jointly as a means to increase credibility and internal validity ((Bryman and Bell, 2007); (Lincoln and Guba, 1985)).

3. The product robustness process

Before displaying and describing the Product Robustness Process (PRP) some of the experiences that motivated the need for this process at MC will be presented. Subsequently, the MC's product development process is introduced, followed by a description of the PRP and outcomes experienced from working with the PRP.

3.1 Experiences that formed the process

A number of experiences have led to the realization of the need of a PRP integrated in the product development process. Initially, the company viewed inferior product reliability primarily as a cause of high warranty costs. Actions to improve reliability were limited to measuring and monitoring the repair rates and customer complaints. In the cases where Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) were applied, it was mainly done in a reactive manner. In other words it was not continuously updated with the purpose of avoiding possible failure modes. The need to further enhance robustness and reliability of the product was based on the realization that inferiority in these aspects not only creates high warranty costs, but also has negative effects on customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The FMEAs are used throughout MC on system, sub-system and component levels. Far too often though, it is used as a tool to identify possible weaknesses in designs and the subsequent parts of the FMEA on failure causes and mitigations are neglected. Besides serving as a tool for failure mode avoidance it is experienced that FMEAs could serve as an overarching document for reliability improvement, incorporating the design history with focus on earlier robustness and reliability issues.

At MC it has been realized that a key to the development of reliable systems is an adequate break-down of system requirements to requirements on sub-systems and components. The reason is experiences of reliability problems being caused by insufficiently specified reliability requirements on sub-systems or components. Clear requirements, traceable to the system level, provide a clear direction for design of sub-systems and components in terms of robustness and reliability.

3.2 The product development process

The product development process at MC is comprised of a number of different phases. In Figure 1 the six phases of the product development process related to the pre-project phase and the design phase are displayed.

Figure 1. The Product Development Process

The pre-project phase involves: identifying the stakeholder needs, translation of needs to verifiable system requirements, and generation, evaluation and selection of concept solutions. Once a concept has been chosen these are further analysed and evaluated. In the last tollgate of the pre-project phase a decision is taken on whether the project should enter the design phase or if it should be terminated. A decision to terminate a project could for example be due to commercial reasons, low technology readiness, or a prediction of low reliability.

The design phase is based on the following stages: system design, detailed design, and verification and validation. In the system design stage the function of the system is broken down into a number of functions of sub-systems and requirements for these sub-systems. The detailed design phase includes the design of components with the starting point from the component requirements. The final activity in the detailed design phase is to verify the design in relation to the stated requirements. The verification and validation phase aims to verify that system requirements are met and that stakeholder' needs are fulfilled.

3.3 The PRP

The PRP is developed specifically to suit the needs and wants of MC, in terms of the company wanting a process focusing on practices and built on their previous experiences and competences. The latter can be exemplified by MC having previous experiences of FMEA and saw it as beneficial if the PRP could be described in ways that indicate where FMEA could be of use. Further, the PRP is focused on activities that should be performed at various stages in product development to foresee and prevent failure modes. An overview of the phases of the PRP and their link to the product development process is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The phases of the product robustness process linked to the product development process

The intent of the PRP is to guide MC’s engineering teams concerning RDM practices applicable in product development. However, even after a concluded product development project robustness efforts are continued, for example through updates of the FMEAs based on field data.

1. Evaluation of system/sub-system concepts

The purpose of this phase is to identify strengths and weaknesses of the evaluated systems/ sub-systems. The inputs to this phase are the initial demands on reliability and robustness. The evaluation of the concepts can, for example, be done by use of P-diagrams, Fault trees, and/or System FMEA. The output from this phase is relative strengths and weaknesses of the concepts. Based on the evaluation, concepts are improved in terms of robustness and

reliability. The output should be one of the inputs to the choice of system/s. This activity should be performed in the Concept Generation and Selection Phase (see Figure 1), hence guiding the concept selection.

2. In-depth system/sub-system risk evaluation

The purpose of the In-depth system/sub-system risk evaluation is to develop the initial technical risk analysis of the chosen concept/s. An important input to this phase is the result of the initial evaluation of the strengths and weaknesses of the chosen concept/s. Initially performed risk analyses should be updated and subsequent mitigation may be necessary. Suitable tools for this phase are for example system FMEAs, P-diagrams, and Variation Modes and Effect Analysis (VMEA) (Chakhunashvili et al., 2003). Besides an updated system risk analysis and an improved concept the output is a decision on whether or not the reliability and robustness risks identified are acceptable. This activity is performed in the “Develop selected concepts” phase (Figure 1), and aims to give an understanding of the inherent robustness of the concept/s chosen.

3. Specification of system reliability requirements

The purpose of this phase is to determine system reliability requirements and to secure the possibility to verify these requirements. Stakeholder needs shall be analysed and reflected in System reliability requirements. The needs should be phrased so that they are possible to verify and have clear acceptance criteria. A draft version of the system reliability requirements should be available in the “Develop selected concepts” phase.

4. System technical risk analysis and mitigation

The purpose of this phase is to identify and eliminate failure modes in the system design. To foresee and prevent possible failure modes the risk analysis from the ‘In-depth system/sub-system risk evaluation’ should be updated and mitigation actions taken. In addition to tools suggested in earlier phases a FMEA focusing on possible risks in the interface between sub-systems or components can be useful. The outputs of this phase are identified failure modes as well as identification of mitigating actions needed. This activity should be performed in the System design phase (Figure 2).

5. Specification of component reliability requirements

The purpose of this phase is to determine the verifiable reliability requirements put on components. This work is carried out within system design as a means to maintain a high-level view when establishing the links between system requirements and requirements of various components. This function, or tolerance chain, should be analysed to assure the possibility to meet the reliability and robustness requirements. Further, it should be used as a basis for determining requirements on component reliability. After this phase it should be possible to design reliable components that assure that the system requirements are fulfilled. This activity should be performed in the System design phase, see Figure 2.

6. Determination of tolerances for components

The purpose of this phase is to assure that system reliability can be met by the manufactured product. Based on the component reliability requirements, tolerances on components need to be determined that assures that the manufactured product will be reliable. Methods for these tolerance stack-up calculations are, for example, worst case tolerancing or process tolerancing. Further, part of the output is to review capabilities of the manufacturing processes to verify that required tolerances can be met. This activity should be performed in the Detailed design phase, see Figure 1.

7. Component technical risk analysis and mitigation

The purpose of this phase is to identify and eliminate failure modes of the component design. The component reliability requirements serve as input to the component technical risk analysis and mitigation. To maximize the quality of the output from this phase it is essential that input data is of good quality. In this phase it may also be suitable to use simulation where the effect of different kinds of loads and design weaknesses can be identified, followed by design improvements. When physical system prototypes are available different design options can be evaluated, preferably by use of Design of Experiments and Accelerated Life Testing. When applicable, Highly Accelerated Life Testing (HALT) can be applied to identify weak areas in the design. This activity is performed in Detailed design.

8. System reliability assessment

The purpose of this phase is to assess whether the system reliability is acceptable or if additional risk mitigation is needed. Drawing on the system design thinking this last phase in the detail design aggregates from the component level to the system level to be able to evaluate the implementation of mitigation activities identified at different levels of design. Thus, it is possible to evaluate whether these efforts are sufficient from a system perspective. The output from this phase should be documented improvements of the design. This activity is to be performed in the Detailed Design phase, see Figure 2.

9. Verification of reliability and robustness

The purpose of this phase is to verify whether robustness and reliability requirements are met. The test methods used in this phase should be set already when the requirements are determined. The verification of design reliability should be performed on component as well as system levels to maximize the chances to identify as many design flaws as possible. This activity should be performed in the Verification of System Design phase.

10. System/Sub-system technical risk analysis update

The purpose of this phase is to update risk analyses based on the results of the system verification and, where needed, mitigate risks. In this phase technical risk analyses on system/sub-system/component levels are updated based on experiences from the earlier phases. If failure modes are identified that were not present in earlier technical risk analyses, or if the likelihood of occurrence of identified failure causes need to be upgraded, actions may be necessary to mitigate the corresponding risks. This activity should be performed in the Verification of System Design phase, see Figure 1.

3.4 Outcomes of the PRP

The PRP has been used at MC for 1.5 years, and is applied in all their product development projects. Due to the project lead times there is not yet a launched product that have been developed following the PRP from phase 1 to 10, hence it is not yet possible to evaluate effects of the PRP in terms of e.g. reduced levels of claims.

At MC, historically, there has been a focus on practices. Especially in a smaller organization a focus on tools could have hindered usage of RDM, as lack of training is often a common excuse for not applying a certain tool and training might be regarded as too costly. Overall, the process has established a framework of practices for how to integrate robust design and systems engineering; adopting a systems view on robust design, focusing relations between system, sub-system and components. Further, the awareness of variation and influential noise factors has increased at MC. The staff feels that the PRP has put focus on noise factors and how these should be dealt with by clever design solutions in early design phases, before simulation models or prototypes are available. This can be exemplified by a P- diagram on a component of MC's product (see Figure 3); the diagram is developed iteratively during the PRP and is a means of assessing and mitigating robustness risks.

Figure 3. P-diagram for one component, to protect confidentiality information has been left out and phrasings have been revised

Use of the PRP has promoted more simulations and prototype tests to identify reliable and robust design solutions in early development phases. As an example, tests performed to assess and improve the performance and reliability of designs were often performed by applying loads equal to what the design should withstand according to the specifications. The conclusion from such tests was often that the design met the requirements and that no further improvements were necessary. After product launch, however, the product quality often proved to be worse than anticipated. To avoid such misjudgements, O'Connor (2002) argues that it is necessary to perform tests where designs are subjected to higher load than expected under operational use. The rationale is that all systems are subject to higher loads than specified, and should be designed to withstand some levels of misuse. In MC tests where the loads on the systems exceeds what is expected under operational use has been applied as a result of the PRP. This reveals possible weaknesses in the design and triggers improvement work.

4. Discussion

At MC the work on robustness and reliability started as a response to high warranty costs. Later it was also acknowledged that reliability and robustness had effects not only in terms of high warranty costs, but also on customer satisfaction and loyalty. Further, management saw possibilities that a more continuous and iterative way of working with certain tools, in particular FMEA, would be beneficial. Eventually questions were raised on how to get robustness and reliability to become an integrated part of the product development process. In essence the PRP was developed in response to these questions. On an overall level, a learning point at MC has been that it is important to promote not only tools but rather elaborate on what activities are needed and the anticipated outputs from these activities. The background is that MC has experiences of other quality related initiatives with strong focus on specific tools. This latter tool oriented strategy has often met resistance as people may have preferences for use of different tools for various reasons, or lack sufficient knowledge to use certain tools.

The design of the PRP is based on two overall ideas; to focus on practices, and to follow up on outcomes or results rather than on use of certain tools. First, the PRP has a strong focus on practices. To ensure that the practices related to RDM are carried out, review questions on robustness are included at the gate reviews in the product development process. This relates to a need for practices in support of continuous applicability of RDM (Hasenkamp et al., 2009). Second, the focus is on activities performed, and the required output from each phase is explicitly stated in the process documentation at the company. As the requirements on certain activities are explicit it is ensured that preventive work e.g. failure mode identification is not neglected.

The fact that the PRP focuses practices and is based on a strategy of non-compulsory use of tools, does not mean that tools that are often used within RDM such as Design of Experiments (DoE) (Box and Jones, 1992) are not feasible to use in the PRP. However, authors like Ford (1996) and Anderson (1997) point to the need of applying RDM efforts in the conceptual design; phases where tools like Design of Experiments might be less useful. As much focus within RDM has been on statistical tools suitable in later design phases the application in concept design can be challenging due to lack of appropriate tools. In MC this was a challenge; however, overcome by a focus on practices and outcomes rather than tools. At gate reviews in the product development process the questions are directed towards what has been done to achieve the outcome required, rather than exactly how it has been done.

An interesting area of future research would be to identify practical strategies to estimate the inherent reliability and robustness of a prototype to give the development teams information on the reliability and robustness of the design at a certain stage in the development process. In other words, an area of research would be to develop a set of indicators evaluating robustness and reliability efforts. Additional areas of future research could be follow-up studies of the result from the PRP, as well as applications in other companies. It is also of interest to evaluate whether or not the process approach applied in this paper is feasible for other companies, or if it could be modified to a set of practices in companies where an additional process is not seen as feasible.

5. Conclusions

The purpose of this paper is to describe and evaluate a process for RDM practices throughout PD. The PRP has been built around the practices of RDM and a focus on the required input and output of each phase, adapted to the characteristics of that specific phase. Thus, in earlier phases like the Evaluation of system/sub-system concepts the input are the demands on reliability and robustness and the output are relative strengths and weaknesses of concepts. The tools suggested for use are hence of a more conceptual nature, in line with what Ford (1996) and Anderson (1997) argue is needed for the use of RDM in conceptual stages of product development.

The PRP specifically focuses on the failure mode avoidance and mitigation; less focus is put on data gathering and estimation of reliability measures for example mean time between failures (MTBF). The results of failure mode avoidance in product design stages are reduced failures in product use stages. Therefore, the PRP contributes to reduced scraps and wastages caused by unreliable products. This could in turn enhance the environmental and economic sustainability.

In summary, three crucial characteristics of the PRP for integration of RDM efforts in the product development work have been identified at MC. First, there is a focus on practices rather than tools. Secondly, the PRP is fully integrated with the product development process and follow up on RDM practices are included at the compulsory gate reviews. Third, the PRP is followed up on RDM related outcomes and not on specific details of how the outcomes were achieved.

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